

THE EFFECTIVENESS OF VILLAGE HEALTH VOLUNTEERS IN HEALTH CARE: A CROSS-SECTIONAL SURVEY IN THAILAND

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Abstract:

Thailand's public health system is strengthened in the form of management. Decentralizing health care across communities can reduce hospitalization rates. The person who is important in this care is the Village Health Volunteer, and encouraging village health volunteers to be able to perform their jobs to the best of their ability will ensure that the process of working in public health can be successful. Objectives to study 1) level of organizational climate, job satisfaction, commitment, and performance effectiveness. 2) Influence of organizational climate, job satisfaction, and commitment to operational effectiveness. This research is quantitative. The sample was 402 Village Health Volunteers using a randomized, segmented method. Collect data using questionnaires Analyze the data with structural equations: 1) The level of the organizational atmosphere is at the highest level, and job satisfaction, engagement, and performance effectiveness are high, 2) the organizational climate, job satisfaction, and commitment has an impact on the operational effectiveness.

Keyword: Health care/ Health management/ Village Health Volunteer

Introduction:

The effectiveness of village health volunteers. It is the result of the performance of volunteer healthcare staff in health care that is important to Thailand's public health system and reflects the quality of the Thai public health system that is strengthened in the management system. Especially during the coronavirus pandemic. Village health volunteers are individuals selected by villagers in each home group and are trained according to the curriculum prescribed by the Ministry of Health. They play an important role as a change agent in public health communications. Introducing, disseminating knowledge, planning, and coordinating public health development activities, as well as providing public health services in areas such as health promotion, disease surveillance, and prevention, primary medical assistance and treatment, using medicines and medical supplies to the extent that the Ministry of Health Schedule referral of patients to rehabilitation services and health consumer protection.

According to the review, the variables associated with the effectiveness of village health volunteers were organization climate, job satisfaction, and employee commitment. Chaudhary, R., Rangnekar, S., and Barua, M.K. (2014) said the perception of the organizational atmosphere emphasizes practical steps, and that behaviors supported by the organization affect work attitudes and can increase job satisfaction. Litwin and Stringer (1974) said that job satisfaction increases work productivity. Reduce the chances of resignation. Absenteeism Job satisfaction

has a positive impact on employee performance. Soomro, B.A., and S, N. (2019) say that engagement is positively correlated with employee performance directly.

According to the review, the organizational climate, job satisfaction, employee commitment, etc. It affects the operational effectiveness of village health volunteers. This leads to research to apply the acquired findings as empirical data to formulate strategies. Policies and guidelines for the performance of village health volunteers are in the best interest of the organization. Specifically, the creation of organizational climate, job satisfaction, and employee commitment aligns with the conceptual framework of the effectiveness of village health volunteers to achieve sustainable organizational goals.

Objective

1. To study the level of organization climate, job satisfaction, employee commitment, and the effectiveness of village health volunteers.
2. To study the influence of the organizational climate, job satisfaction, and employee commitment on the effectiveness of village health volunteers.

A conceptual framework from the relevant literature review is as follows

1. Effectiveness of Work Performance is the result of the competence of employees' effort and support. Employee productivity is reduced if one of the factors is reduced or missing. Many scholars have commented that a person's abilities are the result of talents and interests, as well as training. Developing human resources and having adequate organizational equipment so that employees can work as efficiently as possible. The effectiveness of village health volunteers includes: Teaching and services to provide people with the fastest and most comprehensive health services.
2. Organization climate demonstrates the measurable properties of the work environment through the direct or indirect perception of workers and influences job motivation and employee behavior. Litwin and Stringer (1974) say that an organizational atmosphere is a group of measurable behaviors. The corporate climate can support well-being in the workplace, and improving the organizational atmosphere will greatly affect the performance of employees in the organization.
3. Job satisfaction is an emotional response to various aspects of work, which directly affects the productivity of employees. Feelings of job satisfaction are positive attitudes of employees. This element is consistent with Frederick's (1959) theory that intrinsic motivation factors include job success, recognition, and respect. The nature of the work performed, its responsibilities, and progress. Extrinsic motivation factors include corporate policy, administration, etc. How to govern, and command Interpersonal relationships, working conditions Job security, salary, compensation, benefits, status, position, and relationships with superiors.
4. Employee commitment is the link between employees and the organization. Meyer and Allen (1991) argue that engagement is a psychological state that indicates the strength of an

employee's relationship with the organization. There are three engagement elements: emotions, continuity, and rules, which influence employee outcomes, such as lack of performance and corporate citizenship. A higher level of engagement leads to confidence. Recognition of the goals and values of the organization and employee engagement has a positive relationship with employee productivity and reduce the rate of turnover of employees in the organization.

The review of the relevant literature leads to the formulation of the research conceptual framework as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Conceptual framework

Method

Population and sample

The research population was village health volunteers of Kanchanaburi Province. There are a total of 1,943 personnel.

An example used in this research is Village Health Volunteer The sample size was determined according to the Rule of Thumb (Hair, J.F., Black, W.C., Babin, B.J. and Anderson, R.E. (2010). The sample size was 400 people. Questionnaires with complete information in data analysis, a total of 480 samples, randomly sampled by stratified sampling, found a total of 402 respondents, representing 83.75 percent.

Research tools

1. Characteristics of research tools as a questionnaire which was studied from the literature review and research related to the variables studied in detail the questionnaire is divided into 3 parts:

Part 1 asked about the general status of the respondents, 8 questions, and a checklist questionnaire.

Part 2 questioning the level of performance of the village health volunteers. The questionnaire is a closed-ended question. There are 5 levels of the rating scale, which are the most, the most, the medium, the least, and the least, respectively.

Part 3 asks for other suggestions on ways to improve performance based on the factors presented.

The researcher used the questionnaire to check the quality by determining the content validity by consulting an expert to find confidence and try Out 60 sets. The confidence test was done by using Cronbach's Alpha Coefficient, which was equal to 0.97. And check the construct validity by confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) found that the corporate atmosphere job satisfaction, employee commitment and the effectiveness of the village health volunteers' performance harmonious with empirical data equal to $\chi^2 = 104.187$, $df = 96$, $p\text{-value} = 0.267$, $\chi^2 / pdf = 1.085$, $GFI = 0.977$, $AGFI = 0.951$, $NFI = 0.988$, $RMSEA = 0.014$, $PCLOSE = 1.000$. And analyzed from Factor Factor Loading Score (λ), Composite Reliability (ρ_c), and Average variable extracted (ρ_v). The latent (ρ_c) should be greater than or equal to 0.70 and the extracted variance (ρ_v) should be greater than or equal to 0.50 (Fornell & Larcker, 1981), see in Table 1.

Table 1: Factor Loading Score (λ) show standardize score of latent variables (n = 402)

ตัวแปร	λ	S.E.	t	R ²
Organization climate $\rho_c = 0.93$ $\rho_v = 0.61$	0.78	0.05	16.31***	0.62
Job satisfaction $\rho_c = 0.91$ $\rho_v = 0.83$	0.91	0.02	15.14***	0.83
Employee commitment $\rho_c = 0.84$ $\rho_v = 0.63$	0.79	0.06	10.37***	0.63
Effectiveness of work performance $\rho_c = 0.88$ $\rho_v = 0.72$	0.84	0.04	12.70	0.72

*** It was statistically significant at the .001 level ($p < .001$).

Analysis for the statistical analysis of the questionnaire using a statistical package with the details as follows:

1. Analysis of information about the general status of the respondents the questionnaire is a checklist, using frequency and percentage values.
2. Analysis of the fact-level data of the 5 variables studied. The questionnaire style was closed-ended questions. The rating scale type uses the arithmetic mean method and standard deviation.
3. Analyzing the model according to the research framework. The statistics used were confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) and Structural Equation Modeling (SEM)

Result

The results of a research according to the objectives can be divided into 2 topics as follows:

1. Level of organization climate, job satisfaction, employee commitment, and the effectiveness of the village health volunteers' performance. The results of the research are shown in Table 2.

Table 2: Mean, standard deviation, and level interpretation of the variables studied (n = 402)

Variable	$\bar{x}$	S.D.	Meaning
Organization climate	4.45	0.25	Most
Job satisfaction	3.95	0.28	Lot
Employee commitment	3.67	0.27	Lot
Effectiveness of work performance	4.40	0.22	Lot

From Table 2, the mean latent variables studied were between 3.67– 4.45. With the highest mean, followed by the effectiveness of the village health volunteers' performance, job satisfaction factor, and employee commitment.

Table 3: Results of checking the empirical variable distribution in the structural equation model (n = 402)

Observable variable	$\bar{x}$	S.D.	SK	KU
Organization climate	4.56	0.36	-0.84	3.61
Job satisfaction	2.65	0.16	-0.40	2.12
Employee commitment	2.76	0.28	-0.66	2.58
Effectiveness of work performance	3.54	0.23	-0.17	2.44

From Table 3, it was found that some observable variables had a normal distribution because the kurtosis value exceeded +3.00, but could be used to analyze the structural equation model without violating the preliminary agreement. due to the large sample size ($n > 400$) (Kelloway, 1998).

2. The influence of organizational climate, job satisfaction, and employee commitment. The results of the analysis verify the conformity of the hypothesis-based structural equation model. With the empirical data, it was found that the hypothetical model was not consistent with the empirical data by considering the Fit Index values as follows: $\chi^2 = 684.680$, $df = 161$, $p\text{-value} = .000$, $\chi^2 / df = 4.253$, $GFI = 0.866$, $AGFI = 0.825$, $NFI = 0.919$, $IFI = 0.937$, $CFI = 0.937$, $RMR = 0.014$, $SRMR = 0.038$, $RMSEA = 0.086$, $PCLOSE (p\text{-value for test of close fit}) = 0.000$ and $CN = 124$. As a result, the parameter estimation in the structural equation model is not reliable enough to be practical. The researcher then adjusted the model until the model was consistent with the empirical data as shown in Table 4.

Table 4: Parameter estimation results of the direct effect, indirect effect, and total effect from the modified equation model (n = 402)

Dependent Variable	R ²	Influence	Independent Variable		
			Organization climate	Job satisfaction	Employee commitment
Job satisfaction	0.73	Direct effect	0.85*** (19.19)	-	-
		Indirect effect	-	-	-
		Total effect	0.85*** (19.19)	-	-
Employee commitment	0.93	Direct effect	0.30*** (5.63)	0.70*** (12.02)	-
		Indirect effect	0.59*** (10.24)	-	-
		Total effect	0.89*** (15.39)	0.70*** (12.02)	-
Effectiveness of work performance	0.72	Direct effect	0.43*** (4.32)	0.37* (2.05)	0.09 (0.39)
		Indirect effect	0.39*** (6.58)	0.06 (0.49)	-
		Total effect	0.82*** (13.83)	0.43*** (3.53)	0.09 (0.39)

$\chi^2 = 130.304$, $df = 111$, $p\text{-value} = 0.102$, $\chi^2 / df = 1.174$, $RMSEA = 0.020$, $PCLOSE$ (p-value for test of close fit) = 1.000, $GFI = 0.972$, $AGFI = 0.946$, $NFI = 0.985$, $IFI = 0.998$, $CFI = 0.998$, $RMR = 0.007$, $SRMR = 0.019$ and $CN = 462$

* Statistically significant at .05 (p < .05) *** statistically significant at .001 (p < .001)

Discussion

The effectiveness of the village health volunteers' performance consisted of teaching and service aspects. It was found that the service performance component was the most influential component on the effectiveness of the village health volunteers' performance. In this regard, operational effectiveness can be achieved. Depending on the organization climate with research by Chaur-luh TSAI (2014), it was found that organizational climate was associated with job satisfaction. Especially the corporate atmosphere on the topic of reward. The practice of university staff for some time will create a sense of commitment among employees to create a sense of continuity. And the rewards that a person receives with the basis of expression in the form of behavior which is a manifest expression of feelings that can be measured and evaluated. Consistent with research by Mansour, J.B., Naji, A. and Leclerc, A (2017), job satisfaction was associated with normative engagement and can predict the most engagement with the organization. Rewarding was positively correlated with job satisfaction and organizational commitment. Therefore, from the results of this research, it can be concluded that the performance effectiveness of village health volunteers consists of causal factors such as organizational climate, job satisfaction, and employee commitment that are related to each other. The quality management of the organization's leaders is an important driving force in the successful performance of voluntary healthcare workers in carrying out their stated objectives.

Limitation

This research collected data from a sample of only one province in Thailand. However, future research in the future should collect information that covers the whole country to apply the research findings to use in planning strategies to promote the efficient work of village health volunteers.

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